

EULER PSEUDOPRIMES FOR HALF OF THE BASES

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Received: 5/25/11, Revised: 11/11/11, Accepted: 11/18/11, Published: 10/12/12

Abstract

We prove that an odd number n is an Euler pseudoprime for exactly one half of the admissible bases if and only if n is a special Carmichael number, that is, $a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod n$ for every invertible $a \in \mathbb{Z}_n$.

—Dedicated to the memory of Prof. John Lewis Selfridge

1. Introduction

Given a large odd number n without small factors, one can try to decide whether n is prime by randomly taking some a coprime with n and computing $a^{n-1} \pmod n$. If this value is not 1, then n is certainly not prime, by Fermat’s little theorem. Otherwise we can only say that n is probably prime. Actually either n is prime or n is *pseudoprime* for the base a ; the latter is equivalent to saying that a is a liar to Fermat’s primality test.

Even if Fermat’s primality test is often correct, unfortunately it cannot be trustingly used as a Monte-Carlo primality test because there exist odd composite numbers that are pseudoprimes for all of the bases coprime with n . These numbers are called *Carmichael numbers*: they are much rarer than primes but they are still infinite, as proved by Alford, Granville and Pomerance in [1].

Instead of considering Fermat’s little theorem one could use Euler’s criterion: namely Euler proved that if p is an odd prime, then $a^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{p}\right) \pmod p$ for every a , where $\left(\frac{a}{p}\right)$ is the Legendre–Jacobi symbol. Thus the primality of a large odd number n can be tested by checking $a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \pmod n$ for some a coprime with n . If this relation is not satisfied then n is certainly not prime; otherwise n is probably prime and, as before, we have that either n is prime or n is an *Euler pseudoprime* for the base a ; the latter is equivalent to saying that a is a liar to the Solovay–Strassen primality test.

In order to confidently use this primality test in a Monte-Carlo method, it was very important to establish for how many bases an odd composite number can be an Euler pseudoprime. It has been reported to the author by Pomerance that Selfridge was probably the first one to realize that for every odd composite number n there is at least one x for which n is not an Euler pseudoprime for the base x , but he did not publish his discovery (see [3, Section 5], where Selfridge is credited). Anyway, a few years after Selfridge's discovery, both Lehmer (see [5]) and Solovay–Strassen (see [8]), independently, proved the same result. In particular, Solovay and Strassen also noticed that the subset of bases in $U(\mathbb{Z}_n) := \{a \in \mathbb{Z}_n \mid \gcd(a, n) = 1\}$ for which n is an Euler pseudoprime is actually a subgroup. As an easy consequence of this fact, they showed that no odd composite number can be an Euler pseudoprime for more than half of the admissible bases (that is, elements of the group $U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$):

$$\left| \left\{ a \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n) \mid a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \pmod{n} \right\} \right| \leq \phi(n)/2. \tag{1}$$

This remark paved the way for an efficient probabilistic primality test, named Solovay–Strassen after the two authors.

During the subsequent years many papers about pseudoprimes, Euler pseudoprimes, strong pseudoprimes appeared: for example, an article by Pomerance, Selfridge and Wagstaff ([7]), where many properties are stated and many examples are given and an article by Monier ([6]), where a formula to count the number of liars is given.

The purpose of this note is just to understand in which cases the bound in (1) is actually achieved.

We will prove the following in an equivalent form as Proposition 9:

Proposition 1. *Let n be an odd composite number. Then n is an Euler pseudoprime for exactly one half of the bases in $U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$ if and only if $a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ for every $a \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$.*

2. Preliminary Lemmas

Lemma 2. *Let $n > 2$ be an odd number. Then, for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$, $a^{n-1} \not\equiv -1 \pmod{n}$.*

Proof. Let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r}$, p_i distinct prime numbers. Without loss of generality we can suppose that $\gcd(a, n) = 1$ and that $v := v_2(p_1 - 1) \leq v_2(p_i - 1)$ for all $1 \leq i \leq r$ (v_2 being the dyadic valuation). By contradiction, suppose $a^{n-1} \equiv -1 \pmod{n}$. Then, in particular, $a^{n-1} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_1^{\alpha_1}}$. Let g be a generator for $U(\mathbb{Z}_{p_1^{\alpha_1}})$ and let h be such that $g^h \equiv a \pmod{p_1^{\alpha_1}}$. Then $g^{h(n-1)} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_1^{\alpha_1}}$, that is,

$$\frac{\phi(p_1^{\alpha_1})}{2} \mid h(n-1) \quad \text{but} \quad \phi(p_1^{\alpha_1}) \nmid h(n-1).$$

Hence there exists $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, k odd, such that $\phi(p_1^{\alpha_1})k = 2h(n-1)$, that is, $p_1^{\alpha_1-1}(p_1-1)k = 2h(n-1)$. It follows that $v = v_2(p_1-1) > v_2(n-1)$; however this is not possible since $p_i \equiv 1 \pmod{2^v}$ for every $1 \leq i \leq r$ and thus $n-1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2^v}$. \square

Lemma 3. *Let n be an odd composite number and let $B := \{a \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n) \mid a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{n}\}$. If $|B| \geq \phi(n)/2$, then n is a Carmichael number.*

Proof. If $|B| = \phi(n)$ the statement is trivial; therefore, from now on we can suppose that $|B| = \phi(n)/2$. Let $B' := \{a \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n) \mid a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv +1 \pmod{n}\}$. It is easily seen that two cases can occur: either $B' = B$, that is, B' has index 2 in $U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$, or $C := B \setminus B' \neq \emptyset$ is a coset of B' in $U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$, that is, B' has index 4. In the first case, for any $h \notin B'$ we have $h^2 \in B'$, that is, $h^{n-1} = h^{2 \cdot \frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$. In the second case we can conclude by observing that again $U(\mathbb{Z}_n)/B'$ has elements of order at most 2. Indeed C has order two in $U(\mathbb{Z}_n)/B'$; therefore, if $h \notin B$, then h^2 must be in B' or in C , but the latter is not possible because otherwise $h^{n-1} = h^{2 \cdot \frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv -1 \pmod{n}$, contradicting Lemma 2. \square

Remark 4. Notice that in the proof of Lemma 3 the second case ($C \neq \emptyset$, B' has index 4) does not actually occur. In fact, since we have proved that n is a Carmichael number, we now know that $n = p_1 \cdots p_r$ with $r \geq 3$, p_i distinct primes (see, for example, [4, Proposition V.1.2, Proposition V.1.3]). For every $1 \leq i \leq r$, let g_i be a generator of $U(\mathbb{Z}_{p_i})$. Since $C \neq \emptyset$, there exists $b \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$ such that $b^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv -1 \pmod{n}$, that is, $b^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p_i}$ for every i . In particular $g_i^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p_i}$ for every i . For every $1 \leq i \leq r$, let x_i be the solution \pmod{n} of the system $X \equiv g_i \pmod{p_i}, X \equiv 1 \pmod{n/p_i}$. Notice that for every i , $x_i^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \not\equiv \pm 1 \pmod{n}$ and that for any $i \neq j$, $x_i^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \not\equiv x_j^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \pmod{n}$. Therefore, since $r \geq 3$, B' must have index ≥ 5 .

Lemma 5. *Let $n > 2$ be an odd number. Let*

$$P_n := \left\{ a \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n) \mid \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) = 1 \right\},$$

$$N_n := \left\{ a \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n) \mid \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) = -1 \right\}.$$

If n is not a perfect square then $|P_n| = |N_n| = \phi(n)/2$.

Proof. Notice that we need only to prove that if n is not a perfect square, then $N_n \neq \emptyset$, since in this case N_n is just a coset of the subgroup P_n in $U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$. Let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r}$, p_i distinct primes. Without loss of generality we can suppose that α_1 is odd. Choose $q \in U(\mathbb{Z}_{p_1})$ such that q is not a quadratic residue $\pmod{p_1}$. Let x be any solution of

$$\begin{cases} X \equiv q \pmod{p_1} \\ X \equiv 1 \pmod{p_2 \cdots p_r} \end{cases}$$

Clearly $\gcd(x, n) = 1$. Moreover

$$\left(\frac{x}{n}\right) = \left(\frac{x}{p_1}\right)^{\alpha_1} \cdots \left(\frac{x}{p_r}\right)^{\alpha_r} = (-1)^{\alpha_1} = -1,$$

that is, $N_n \neq \emptyset$. □

3. Special Carmichael Numbers

Definition 6. Let n be an odd composite number. We say that n is a *special Carmichael number* if $a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod n$ for all $a \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$.

Following Korselt, we have the characterization below:

Proposition 7. *A positive integer n is a special Carmichael number if and only if n is odd, square-free and $(p-1) \mid \frac{n-1}{2}$ for every prime p such that $p \mid n$.*

Proof. Just a minor modification of Korselt’s proof is needed (see, for example, [4, Proposition V.I.2]). □

Remark 8. It is clear that special Carmichael numbers are Carmichael numbers. As explained in [2, Exercise 3.24] the proof of the infinitude of Carmichael numbers (see [1]) actually implies that there are infinitely many special Carmichael numbers. The least example is the famous “taxicab” number 1729, dear to Hardy and Ramanujan. The first elements of the sequence of special Carmichael numbers are 1729, 2465, 15841, 41041, 46657, 75361, 162401, 172081, 399001, 449065, 488881, . . . It is also clear from Proposition 7 that every special Carmichael number must be $\equiv 1 \pmod 4$.

We are now ready to prove our main result.

Proposition 9. *Let n be an odd composite number. Then n is an Euler pseudoprime for exactly one half of the bases in $U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$ if and only if n is a special Carmichael number.*

Proof. If n is a special Carmichael number then, in particular, n is a Carmichael number and thus n is square-free. Therefore, by Lemma 5, n is an Euler pseudoprime for half of the bases in $U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$, namely for all $a \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$ such that $\left(\frac{a}{n}\right) = 1$.

Conversely, suppose that n is an Euler pseudoprime for exactly one half of the bases in $U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$. Then by hypothesis $a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv \pm 1 \pmod n$ for at least one half of the admissible bases and therefore, in particular, n is a Carmichael number by Lemma 3, thus $n = p_1 \cdots p_r$, p_i distinct primes, $r \geq 3$. By [2, Exercise 3.24] and Remark 4, either $a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod n$ for every $a \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$ or $a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod n$ for exactly one

half of the admissible bases (while $a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \not\equiv \pm 1 \pmod n$ for the other half). We must rule out the latter case.

By hypothesis and by Lemma 5, $\left(\frac{a}{n}\right) = 1$ for all $a \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$ such that $a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod n$, while $\left(\frac{a}{n}\right) = -1$ for all $a \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$ such that $a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \not\equiv 1 \pmod n$. We will now exhibit $x \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$ such that $x^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \not\equiv 1$ but $\left(\frac{x}{n}\right) = 1$, a contradiction.

Let $b \in U(\mathbb{Z}_n)$ such that $b^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \not\equiv 1$. In particular, there exists a prime factor p of n , say p_1 , such that $b^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p_1}$. Let g be a generator of $U(\mathbb{Z}_{p_1})$, so that $g^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p_1}$. Let g' be a generator of $U(\mathbb{Z}_{p_2})$. Let x be the unique solution mod n of the system

$$\begin{cases} X \equiv g & \pmod{p_1} \\ X \equiv g' & \pmod{p_2} \\ X \equiv 1 & \pmod{p_3 \cdots p_r} \end{cases}$$

We see immediately that $x^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \not\equiv 1 \pmod n$ and

$$\left(\frac{x}{n}\right) = \prod_{i=1}^r \left(\frac{x}{p_i}\right) = (-1)(-1) = 1.$$

□

Remark 10. As Pomerance kindly pointed out to the author, Proposition 9 can also be proved by a careful consideration of all the cases in Monier’s formula for the number of liars to the Solovay–Strassen test (see [6, Prop. 3] and [3]). Actually Monier, in [6], also observes that odd composite numbers achieving the bound in (1) are Carmichael numbers, but he does not make calculations explicit and misses to give a complete characterization (although he was probably aware of the gist of Proposition 9). It is also worth remarking that Monier, in [6], additionally gives a formula for the number of liars to the Miller–Rabin test. This formula can be used to give a complete characterization of odd composite numbers n achieving the bound $\phi(n)/4$ for strong pseudoprimes: see [6] and [9, Equation 1.5 and Section 5].

Acknowledgments The author wishes to warmly thank Prof. C. Pomerance for his kindness and for many helpful discussions.

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